

ISSUES OF INCREASING TEACHER'S INFLUENCE IN EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER CONDITIONS

Khimmataliev Dustnazar Omonovich

doctor of pedagogic sciences, professor, Chirchik State Pedagogical University,
d.ximmataliev@mail.ru

Omonova Munisa Dustnazar qizi

National University of Uzbekistan 4th year student

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***Abstract.** The educational cluster is of great importance in forming the professional reputation of future teachers. The article highlights the issues of increasing the teacher's professional authority, which is manifested in interactions with communities engaged in social, professional, cultural activities.*

***Key words:** influence, cluster, profession, culture, attitude, experience, initiative, project, entrepreneurship.*

An important component of educational clusters for the training of future teachers is the creation of internships as a personnel, information, scientific and methodological resource base on the basis of an educational institution. The possibilities of additional education in the formation of a person's pedagogical direction are great. From a social point of view, it helps to determine one's position in the professional process and life situations. From a cultural point of view, educational clusters allow to significantly expand the range of relations with accumulated eternal values. In the pedagogical sense, pedagogical education creates a broad general cultural-emotional background for mastering.

An important feature of the educational cluster, which is of great importance in the formation of the professional reputation of future teachers, is openness, which is manifested in social, professional, cultural and recreational interactions with groups of adults and peers who are engaged in the same or similar type of activity. The opportunity for teachers and students to include current events of socio-cultural reality, their living and reflection experience in the educational process, favorable conditions for the creation and implementation of public initiatives and projects for both children (adolescents) and adults, including volunteering and social entrepreneurship, leads to development.

Prospective models of ensuring the professional reputation of professors and teachers in the context of an educational cluster include:

- pedagogical practice system;
- a system of regular seminars on current issues;
- development of the educational system;
- a system of problem seminars organized on the basis of the study of educational needs and difficulties;
- scientific-practical conferences;
- network methodical associations on various directions and activities of children's education;
- thematic methodical weeks and methodical days;

- pedagogical skill school: round talks, master classes, pedagogical drawing rooms, pedagogical readings;

- methodological tips: individual, group, frontal.

Thus, the educational cluster is a holistic education that includes organizational, managerial, technological, and content levels that enable the implementation of the target process as the main component and the most important condition of the model of continuous training of pedagogical personnel.

The prestige of the teaching profession is more affected by parents who tend to shift responsibility for the upbringing and education of their children. First of all, every teacher should protect his good name. And this is true, because respect for the teacher is formed in every lesson from the first lesson: his attitude to students, his knowledge of the subject, his ability to find a suitable way out of difficult pedagogical situations, his appearance, personal qualities, compliance with certain moral rules. In recent years, the work of teachers has become much more difficult. The reason is that until recently they were the most educated people in society. Today, students' parents are candidates of science, doctors of science, most of them have higher education. But the world cannot be turned back. Therefore, the teacher must constantly improve his profession, otherwise the respect for him will quickly disappear. And yet, in any situation, he must be loyal to his work. A person who knows how to respect himself will be respected by others. A person who is ashamed of his profession unknowingly creates a negative attitude towards himself and his work. In our country, education has always played a major role in shaping society and enriching culture. Throughout its historical development, it has influenced the widest strata of the population, due to which it has become an important spiritual and professional basis in people's lives. Educational problems literally belong to every citizen, because the process of education and upbringing occupies a special place in the biography of any person.

What is influence?

Prestige is influence or respect over someone or something.

Prestige - the level of prestige, influence, respect in society corresponds to a certain social status.

To increase the prestige of the teaching profession, it is desirable to perform the following tasks:

1. Optimizing the composition of teachers and administration in terms of age;
2. To increase the percentage of young teachers involved in work up to 30%;
3. Increase the share of graduates of secondary special vocational education institutions trained according to the higher and target program;
4. Increasing the weight of teachers who participated in pedagogical and professional skill competitions to 25%;
5. Increase the weight of teachers involved in innovative activities up to 26%;
6. Timely social support of teachers;
7. Increasing the number of students directed to admission to pedagogical professions;
8. To systematically cover the professional activities of teachers in mass media.

In today's complex socio-economic conditions, the prestige of the teaching profession cannot be described by one word "low" or "high". Reputation is a multifaceted phenomenon. It is determined by the comparative assessment of the social importance of various objects by the society, the functional importance of the profession, the respect that a certain person enjoys as a

representative of a certain profession, and the level of recognition. This is a unique valuable quality that predetermines a person's choice of a particular profession.

The prestige of the teaching profession is defined as the interaction of public evaluations and subjective opinions regarding the teacher's own profession. The prestige of the teaching profession largely depends on the prestige of education in society. In the conditions of socio-economic development of the country, the need for education is gaining a new meaning, and in this regard, the prestige of the teaching profession is steadily increasing.

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